

Some remarks concerning on a fuzzy real normed space

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ABSTRACT

In mathematics, computer science, statistics, and other fields, the notion of fuzzy metric and fuzzy normed is crucial. Finding an acceptable fuzzy metric or norm for making some measurements can solve a lot of difficulties. In the sense of Mohammedali, fuzzy real normed spaces (FRNS) are the issue of this paper. Real normed and fuzzy real normed are advanced together with a ground-breaking analysis of their interactions. The structure of FRNS in terms of families of sublinear functional is established. After investigating some properties of "sublinear functional" that corresponding to an FRN, the concept of the family of star sublinear functional based on the popular t-conorm (a parameter some families) is introduced with proved that a descending and separating family of star sublinear functional, denoted by Q^* produces a FRNS. In addition, the concept of generating space of quasinorm and quasi-norm family (GSQNF) has been presented. Furthermore, the decomposition theorem of a FRN \tilde{N}_f into a family of quasinorm is formulated. The correlation between FRNS and the quasinorm family's generating space is explored and demonstrated.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Imprecise data is used in a variety of real-world problems in engineering, medical sciences, social sciences, economics, agriculture, and other fields, and their solution requires the application of mathematical principles based on uncertainty and imprecision. Probability, fuzzy set theory, intuitionistic fuzzy set, hazy set, theory of interval mathematics, and other topics are used to deal with such uncertainty. Zadeh [1] proposed the concept of a fuzzy set. As a result, fuzzy set theory has applications in various fields of mathematics as well as other sciences [2]-[12]. The concept of fuzzy metric spaces was presented by Kramosil and Michalek [13]. Fuzzy normed spaces are an important type of fuzzy metric space that provides a suitable framework for inexact measurements of ordinary lengths in linear space. In recent years, the research of fuzzy normed spaces and probabilistic normed spaces has gotten a lot of interest (see for instance [14]-[21]). On the other hand, Bag and Samanta [22] looked at a general t-norm in the notion of fuzzy normed linear space presented in [23], and showed that if the t-norm isn't "min," the decomposition theorem of fuzzy norm may not hold. On the other hand, the idea of a fuzzy norm on a real linear space based on the concept of continuous triangular conorm (t-conorm) was suggested in the paper [24]. On the basis of this idea, and given the importance of the decomposition theorem in the development of fuzzy functional analysis and its applications, it is worthwhile to construct a new type of fuzzy real norm decomposition theorem based on a t-conorm. This is one of the work's objectives. How far the outcomes of fuzzy real normed space (FRNS) can be established using the FRN in its general form, that is, by ignoring the restricted "max" t-conorm in the triangle inequality. Addressing this issue is to other objective of this work.

This work is structured as follows: section 2 comprises some preliminary results. In section 3, a formulation of the structure of FRNS in terms of families of sublinear functional based on the particular choice of (max) t-conorm is presented, as well as some fundamental results. In section 4, the concept of a quasinorm family and generating space of quasi-norm family (GSQNF) are given. Moreover, it is investigated how FRNS and GSQNF interact.

2. SOME PRELIMINARY RESULTS

In FRNS, which were offered on Mohammedali viewpoint, there are some fundamental hypotheses and significant findings. We will provide the background information and supplemental findings that are required. An definition of a fuzzy real normed space is now provided.

Definition 2.1. [24]: Let Δ_c be a triangular t- conorm, V be a linear space over the field \mathbf{R} . The fuzzy norm \tilde{N}_f on V is a fuzzy subset mapping $\tilde{N}_f: V \times [0, \infty)$ into I if the following requirements apply $\forall v_1, v_2 \in V$ and $\forall t \in [0, \infty)$;

$$(RN1) \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) > 0, \text{ for all } t > 0$$

$$(RN2) \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) = 1 \text{ if and only if } v_1 = 0, \text{ for all } t > 0$$

$$(RN3) \forall r \neq 0 \in \mathbf{R}, \tilde{N}_f(r v_1, t) = \tilde{N}_f\left(v_1, \frac{t}{|r|}\right)$$

$$(RN4) \tilde{N}_f(v_1 + v_2, t) \leq \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) \Delta_c \tilde{N}_f(v_2, t)$$

$$(RN5) \tilde{N}_f(v_1, \cdot): (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0,1] \text{ is continuous with respect to } t$$

Consequently, $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ is known as FRNS.

We suppose that the fuzzy real norm also meets the following criterion in order to get some significant results.

$$(RN6) \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) > 0, \forall t > 0 \Rightarrow v_1 = 0$$

Lemma 2.2. [24]: Let $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ be a FRNS. Then $\tilde{N}_f(v_1 - v_2, t) = \tilde{N}_f(v_2 - v_1, t) \forall v_1, v_2 \in V$ and $t > 0$.

Example 2.3. [24]: Let $(R^2, || \cdot ||)$ be a normed space, where $V = R^2$ is a linear space which is obtained if the set of ordered pairs of real numbers $v_1 = (\rho_1, \rho_2) \in R^2$ is taken with a function $||v_1|| = ||v_1|| = (|\rho_1|^2 + |\rho_2|^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. Define $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) = ||v_1|| - t / t + ||v_1||$ for $t < ||v_1||$ and $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) = 0 \forall t \geq ||v_1||$. Also $a \Delta_c b = a + b - ab$ for all $a, b \in I$. Then $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ is FRNS.

Definition 2.4. [24]: Let $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ be a FRN. Open is the name for the set A of V if for any point $v_1 \in V \exists$ an $\alpha \in (0,1)$ center v_1 and radius, $B(v_1, \alpha, t) = \{v_2 \in V, \tilde{N}_f(v_1, v_2, t) > 1 - \alpha\}$ is contained entirely in A .

Definition 2.5. [24]: A sequence $\{v_n\}$ in a FRNS $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ is said to be \check{l} -convergent if there exists a vector v in V such that $\tilde{N}_f(v_n - v, t) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, for all $t > 0$.

Definition 2.6. [24]: A sequence $\{v_n\}$ in a FRNS $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ is said \check{l} -Cauchy sequence if $\lim \tilde{N}_f(v_n v_{n+s}) = 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty, s > 0$ and $\forall t > 0$.

Definition 2.7. [24]: A FRNS $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ is said to be \check{l} -complete if every \check{l} -Cauchy sequence in V is \check{l} -convergent.

3. SUBLINEAR FUNCTIONAL STRUCTURES IN A FRNS

This section focuses on formulating the structure of FRNS in terms of families of sublinear functional based on the particular choice of (max) t-conorm with investigating some properties of sublinear functional corresponding to a FRN. The concept of a family of star sublinear functional based on the popular

t-conorm (a parameter some families) is established. Furthermore, a descending and separating family of star sublinear functions, referred to as Q^* has been proven to produce FRN.

A sublinear functional is given in [25] as: Let V be a linear space. The function q_α from V into \mathbf{R} is called sublinear functional on V if the following conditions are satisfied.

$$\text{i) } q_\alpha(\rho v_1) = \rho q_\alpha(v_1) \quad \forall v_1 \in V \text{ and } \rho \in (0, \infty)$$

$$\text{ii) } q_\alpha(v_1) + q_\alpha(v_2) \geq q_\alpha(v_1 + v_2) \quad \forall v_1, v_2 \in V$$

The following theorem gives a new characterization of sublinear functional family on V .

Theorem 3.1: Let $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ be a FRNS where $\Delta_c = (max)$ and let $0 < \alpha < 1$. The function $q_\alpha(\cdot): V \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is given by;

$$q_\alpha(v_1) = \inf \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\} \quad (1)$$

Then $Q = \{q_\alpha : 0 < \alpha < 1\}$ is a decreasing family of sublinear functional on V .

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i) For } \rho \in (0, \infty), \text{ we have } q_\alpha(\rho v_1) &= \inf \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(\rho v_1, t) < \alpha\} \\ &= \inf \left\{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f\left(v_1, \frac{t}{|\rho|}\right) < \alpha\right\} \\ &= \inf \left\{|\rho| \frac{t}{|\rho|} > 0: \tilde{N}_f\left(v_1, \frac{t}{|\rho|}\right) < \alpha\right\} \\ &= |\rho| \inf \left\{\frac{t}{|\rho|} > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\right\} = |\rho| q_\alpha(v_1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii) } q_\alpha(v_1) + q_\alpha(v_2) &= \inf \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\} + \inf \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_2, t) < \alpha\}, \quad \forall 0 < \alpha < 1 \\ &= \inf \{2t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha, \tilde{N}_f(v_2, t) < \alpha\} \\ &= \inf \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1 + v_2) < \alpha \Delta_c \alpha\} \\ &\geq \inf \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1 + v_2, t) < \alpha\} = q_\alpha(v_1 + v_2) \end{aligned}$$

it remains to be proven that Q is a decreasing family. For $0 < \alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < 1$, we note $\{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha_2\} \subseteq \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha_1\}$. Thus $\inf \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha_1\} \geq \inf \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha_2\}$, namely $q_{\alpha_1}(v_1) \geq q_{\alpha_2}(v_1) \quad \forall v_1 \in V$.

The sublinear functional corresponding to a FRN (\tilde{N}_f) behaves as stated in the following proposition.

Proposition 3.2: Let $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ be an FRNS and $q_\alpha(v_1) = \inf \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\}, 0 < \alpha < 1$. Then $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, l) < \alpha$ and only if $q_{\alpha_1}(v_1) < l$ for $v_1 \in V, l > 0$ and $0 < \alpha < 1$.

Proof:

As $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, l) < \alpha$, we obtain that $l \in \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\}$. Thus $q_\alpha(v_1) \leq l$. We presume that $q_\alpha(v_1) = l$. Since $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, \cdot)$ is continuous in l then $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) = \tilde{N}_f(v_1, l)$. Thus $\exists t_0 < l$ with $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t_0) < \alpha$. (Contrary, $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) \geq \alpha, \forall t \leq l$. Therefore $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) \geq \alpha$ so $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, l) \geq \alpha$, which is a contradiction). But $t_0 < l$ with $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t_0) < \alpha$ are in contradiction with the fact that $l = \inf \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\}$. Thus $q_\alpha(v_1) \neq l$. Hence $q_\alpha(v_1) < l$.

Conversely, we must show that $l \in \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\}$. We assume that $l \notin \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\}$, then $\exists t_0 \in \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\}$ with $t_0 < l$. (Contrary, $l \leq t, \forall t \in \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\}$. So $\leq \inf \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\}$, this means $l \leq q_\alpha(v_1)$ which is contradiction). As $t_0 \in \{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\}$, $t_0 < l$ and $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, \cdot)$ is decreasing, we obtain that $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, l) \leq \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t_0) < \alpha$. Therefore, $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, l) < \alpha$, which leads to a contradiction.

The following theorem characterizes an open set.

Theorem 3.3: Let $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ be a FRNS with $\Delta_c = (max)$. If E is open set in $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ then:

$$E = \{v_1 \in V, q_\alpha(v_1) < t\} \quad (2)$$

Proof:

Let $B = \{v_1 \in V, q_\alpha(v_1) < t\}$. Suppose that $v_1 \in E$ then $\exists 0 < l < 1, t \in R^+$ and $t > 0$ with $B(v_1, l, t) \subset E$ then $B(v_1, l, t) = \{v_2 \in V: \tilde{N}_f(v_1 - v_2, t) < 1 - l\} \subset E$. Now, if $v_2 = 0$ in V (since V linear space) then $B(v_1, l, t) = \{0 \in V: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < 1 - l\} \subset E$. Let $1 - l \geq \alpha$ then $0 < \alpha < 1$ this implies that $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha$ thus $q_\alpha(v_1) < t$, i.e $v_1 \in B$. If $v_2 \neq 0$ then $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) = \tilde{N}_f(v_1 - v_2 + v_2, t) \leq \tilde{N}_f(v_1 - v_2, t) \Delta_c \tilde{N}_f(v_2, t) < (1 - l) \Delta_c \tilde{N}_f(v_2, t)$. $\tilde{N}_f(v_2, t) \neq 1$ because $v_2 \neq 0$ and $\tilde{N}_f(v_2, t) > 0$ then $0 < \tilde{N}_f(v_2, t) < 1$. Assume that $l^* = \tilde{N}_f(v_2, t)$ then $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < 1 - l \Delta_c l^* = \alpha, 0 < \alpha < 1$, it means that $E \subset B$.

Conversely, suppose that $v_1 \in B$ then $q_\alpha(v_1) < t$ this implies that $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha, 0 < \alpha < 1$. Let $1 - \alpha = l, 0 < l < 1$ then $1 - l \leq \alpha$ it suggests that $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < 1 - l = \tilde{N}_f(v_1 - 0, t) < 1 - l$, it signifies that $B(v_1, l, t) \subset E$, i.e., $v_1 \in E$. Therefore, $E = \{v_1 \in V: q_\alpha(v_1) < t\}$.

Definition 3.4: Let V be a linear space, Δ_c be a continuous t-conorm. $q_\alpha^*: V \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ is a function for each $0 < \alpha < 1$. $Q^* = \{q_\alpha^*, 0 < \alpha < 1\}$ is called a family of star sublinear functional if it satisfies the following conditions, $\forall v_1, v_2 \in V, 0 < \alpha, \beta < 1$ and $\rho \geq 0$:

$$(Q_1^*) q_\alpha^*(\rho v_1) = \rho q_\alpha^*(v_1)$$

$$(Q_2^*) q_\alpha^*(\rho v_1) + q_\beta^*(v_2) \geq q_{\alpha \Delta_c \beta}^*(v_1 + v_2)$$

if Q^* satisfies the condition $(Q_3^*) q_\alpha^*(v_1) = 0 \forall 0 < \alpha < 1$ implies $v_1 = 0$, then Q^* is said to be separating.

Remark 3.5: from (Q_1^*) , we conclude that $q_\alpha(0) = 0 \forall 0 < \alpha < 1$.

Definition 3.6: $q_\alpha^*(.)$ is said to be continuous with respect to $0 < \alpha < 1$ if for any sequence (α_n) in $(0, 1)$ with $\alpha_n \rightarrow \alpha$ implies $q_{\alpha_n}^*(v_1) \rightarrow q_\alpha^*(v_1) \forall v_1 \in V$.

The following theorem constructs a FRNS of a star sublinear functional family when the family Q^* satisfies the criteria for descending and separating.

Theorem 3.7: Let V be a real linear space and $Q^* = \{q_\alpha^*(.) : 0 < \alpha < 1\}$ be a sufficient, descending and separating family of star sublinear functional satisfies that $q_\alpha^*(.)$ is continuing in respect to $0 < \alpha < 1$. Define a function $\tilde{N}_f^*: V \times [0, \infty) \rightarrow I$ as;

$$\tilde{N}_f^*: (v_1, t) = \begin{cases} \inf \{ \alpha \in (0, 1) : q_\alpha(v_1) < t, & \text{if } t > 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } \{ \alpha \in (0, 1) : q_\alpha(v_1) < t \} = \emptyset \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Then \tilde{N}_f^* is a FRN on V .

Proof:

(RN₁) Is obvious.

(RN₂) If $v_1 = 0$, then $q_\alpha^*(v_1) = 0 < t \forall t > 0$ from Remark 3.5. Hence $\tilde{N}_f^*(v_1, t) = 1$. Conversely, if $\tilde{N}_f^*(v_1, t) = 1 \forall t > 0$, then $q_\alpha^*(v_1) < t \forall 0 < \alpha < 1$ so $q_\alpha^*(v_1) = 0 \forall 0 < \alpha < 1$. Since Q^* is separating, then $v_1 = 0$.

(RN₃) Let $r \neq 0 \in R$, then $\tilde{N}_f^*(rv_1, t) = \inf \{ \alpha \in (0, 1) : q_\alpha^*(rv_1) < t \}$
 $= \inf \{ \alpha \in (0, 1) : q_\alpha^*(v_1) < \frac{t}{|r|} \} = \tilde{N}_f^*(v_1, \frac{t}{|r|})$.

(RN₄) Let $v_1, v_2 \in V$ and $t > 0$. Then $\tilde{N}_f^*(v_1 + v_2, t) = \inf \{ \alpha \in (0, 1) : q_\alpha^*(v_1 + v_2) < t \}$. Now, $\tilde{N}_f^*(v_1, t) = \inf \{ \alpha \in (0, 1) : q_\alpha^*(v_1) < t \} = \bar{\alpha}$ (say) and $\tilde{N}_f^*(v_2, t) = \inf \{ \beta \in (0, 1) : q_\beta^*(v_2) < t \} = \bar{\beta}$ (say) where $q_{\bar{\alpha}}^*(v_1) = t$ and $q_{\bar{\beta}}^*(v_2) = t$. (Since $q_\alpha^*(.)$ is continuing in respect to $0 < \alpha < 1$). Now,

$$\tilde{N}_f^*(v_1, t) \Delta_c \tilde{N}_f^*(v_2, t) = \bar{\alpha} \Delta_c \bar{\beta} \tag{4}$$

and

$$q_{\bar{\alpha} \Delta_c \bar{\beta}}^*(v_1 + v_2) \leq q_{\bar{\alpha}}^*(v_1) + q_{\bar{\beta}}^*(v_2) = 2t \tag{5}$$

this implies that $\tilde{N}_f^*(v_1 + v_2) \leq \bar{\alpha} \Delta_c \bar{\beta} = \tilde{N}_f^*(v_1, t) \Delta_c \tilde{N}_f^*(v_2, t)$.

(RN₅) Let (t_n) be a sequence in $[0, \infty)$ with $t_n \rightarrow t$. Now, $\forall v_1 \in V$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{N}_f^*(v_1, t_n) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} [\inf \{ \alpha \in (0, 1) : q_\alpha^*(v_1) < t_n \}] \\ &= \inf \{ \alpha \in (0, 1) : q_\alpha^*(v_1) < \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} t_n \} \\ &= \inf \{ \alpha \in (0, 1) : q_\alpha^*(v_1) < t \} = \tilde{N}_f^*(v_1, t). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\tilde{N}_f^*(v_1, t_n) \rightarrow \tilde{N}_f^*(v_1, t)$. It means that $\tilde{N}_f^* : [0, \infty) \rightarrow t$ is continuous with respect to t .

4. CREATING SPACE OF QUASINORM FAMILY

In this section, the concept of generating space of quasinorm and quasinorm family are presented. Moreover, the decomposition theorem for a FRN (\tilde{N}_f) with general t-conorm into a family of quasinorm is established. In addition The concepts of various \tilde{l} -convergent sequences types, \tilde{l} -Cauchy sequences, an \tilde{l} -completeness of a fuzzy real normed space, etc. are presented, and the relationships between these conceptions are analyzed.

In the definition that follows, the idea of GSQNF is introduced.

Definition 4.1: Let V be a linear space over the field R . Let $Q = \{q_\alpha(\cdot), 0 < \alpha < 1\}$ be a family of mappings from V into $[0, \infty)$. Q is called a quasinorm family and (V, Q) is called GSQNF if the following conditions are satisfied $\forall v_1, v_2 \in V, \rho \in R$.

$$(QRN_1) \quad q_\alpha(v_1) = 0, \forall 0 < \alpha < 1 \text{ if and only if } v_1 = 0$$

$$(QRN_2) \quad q_\alpha(\rho v_1) = |\rho| q_\alpha(v_1), \forall 0 < \alpha < 1$$

$$(QRN_3) \quad \text{For any } 0 < \alpha < 1, \exists \beta \in (0, \alpha] \text{ with } q_\alpha(v_1 + v_2) \leq q_\beta(v_1) + q_\beta(v_2)$$

$$(QRN_4) \quad \text{If } 0 < \alpha \leq \beta < 1 \text{ then } q_\alpha(v_1) \geq q_\beta(v_1)$$

The following theorem illustrates how a FRN \tilde{N}_f based on (t-conorm) can be decomposed into a family of quasinorms.

Theorem 4.2: Let $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ be a FRNS with Δ_c is upper semi-continuous. Define:

$$q_\alpha(v_1) = \inf \{ t > 0, \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha \} \text{ for } 0 < \alpha < 1 \quad (6)$$

and $Q = \{q_\alpha(\cdot), 0 < \alpha < 1\}$ then (V, Q) is a GSQNF.

Proof:

(QRN₁) Let $q_\alpha(v_1) = 0 \forall 0 < \alpha < 1$ then $\inf \{ t > 0 : \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha \} = 0, \forall 0 < \alpha < 1$. Suppose that $\epsilon_0 > 0$ be given then $\inf \{ t > 0 : \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha \} < \epsilon_0, \forall 0 < \alpha < 1$ implies that $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, \epsilon_0) < \alpha, \forall 0 < \alpha < 1$ so $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, \epsilon_0) = 1$. Since $\epsilon_0 > 0$ is arbitrary then, $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) = 1 \forall t > 0$ hence $v_1 = 0$.

Conversely, Let $v_1 = 0$ and $0 < \alpha < 1$ then by (RN₂), $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) = 1, \forall t > 0$ this suggests that $\tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha, \forall t > 0$ means $q_\alpha(v_1) = 0$. Since $0 < \alpha < 1$ is arbitrary hence $q_\alpha(v_1) = 0, \forall 0 < \alpha < 1$.

(QRN₂) Let $v_1 \in V, \rho \in R$ and $0 < \alpha < 1$ then:

$$\begin{aligned} q_\alpha(\rho v_1) &= \inf \{ t > 0, \tilde{N}_f(\rho v_1, t) < \alpha \} \\ &= \inf \left\{ t > 0, \tilde{N}_f \left(v_1, \frac{t}{|\rho|} \right) < \alpha \right\} \\ &= \inf \left\{ |\rho| \cdot \frac{t}{|\rho|} > 0, \tilde{N}_f \left(v_1, \frac{t}{|\rho|} \right) < \alpha \right\} \\ &= |\rho| \inf \left\{ |\rho| \cdot \frac{t}{|\rho|}, \tilde{N}_f \left(v_1, \frac{t}{|\rho|} \right) < \alpha \right\} = |\rho| q_\alpha(v_1) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

(QRN₃) since Δ_c is upper semi-continuous, for any $0 < \alpha < 1, \exists \beta \in (0, \alpha]$ with $\beta \Delta_c \beta \leq \alpha$.

Now, $q_\beta(v_1) + q_\beta(v_2) = \inf \{ t > 0 : \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \beta \} + \inf \{ t > 0 : \tilde{N}_f(v_2, t) < \beta \}$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \inf\{2t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \beta, \tilde{N}_f(v_2, t) < \beta\} \\ &\geq \inf\{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1 + v_2, t) < \beta \Delta_c \beta \leq \alpha\} \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

(QRN₄) suppose that $v_1 \in V, 0 < \alpha, \beta < 1$ then for $\alpha < \beta$ we note $\inf\{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \alpha\} \geq \inf\{t > 0: \tilde{N}_f(v_1, t) < \beta\}$, it means $q_\alpha(v_1) \geq q_\beta(v_1)$.

Therefore, $Q = \{q_\alpha(\cdot): 0 < \alpha < 1\}$ is quasinorm family on V and (V, Q) is a GSQNF.

Definition 4.3: Let (V, Q) be GSQNF and v_n be a sequence in V . Then (v_n) is said to be \check{L} -convergent if $\exists v \in V$ with $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} q_\alpha(v_n - v) = 0 \forall 0 \leq \alpha < 1$.

Definition 4.4: Let (V, Q) be a gsqnf and v_n be a sequence in V . Then (v_n) is said to be \check{L} -Cauchy sequence, if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} q_\alpha |v_{n+s} - v_n| = 0 \forall 0 \leq \alpha < 1, s > 0$.

Definition 4.5: A GSQNF (V, Q) is said to be \check{L} -complete if every \check{L} -Cauchy sequence in V converge to some point in V .

This section's final propositions are devoted to demonstrating how FRNS and GSQNF are related.

Proposition 4.6: Let $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ be a FRNS satisfying (RN₆). If (x_n) be sequence in V , then (v_n) is \check{L} -convergent to v with respect to Q if and only if (v_n) is \check{L} -converges to v with respect to \tilde{N}_f .

Proof:

Let (v_n) be a sequence in V , with (v_n) is \check{L} -converges to V with respect to Q . Consider $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} q_\alpha(v_n - v) = 0 \forall 0 < \alpha < 1$. Then corresponding to any $t > 0, \exists n_0(\alpha, t) > 0$ with $q_\alpha(v_n - v) < t, \forall n \geq n_0(\alpha, t) \rightarrow \tilde{N}_f(v_n - v, t) < \alpha, \forall n \geq n_0(\alpha, t) \rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{N}_f(v_n - v, t) < \alpha, \forall 0 < \alpha < 1 \rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{N}_f(v_n - v, t) = 1, \forall t > 0$.

Conversely, Let (v_n) be a sequence in V with (v_n) is \check{L} -converges to v with respect to \tilde{N}_f means $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{N}_f(v_n - v, t) = 1 \forall t > 0$. We choose $0 \leq \alpha < 1 \rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{N}_f(v_n - v, t) < \alpha, \forall t > 0 \rightarrow \exists n_0(\alpha, t) > 0$ with $\tilde{N}_f(v_n - v, t) < \alpha \forall n \geq n_0(\alpha, t) \rightarrow q_\alpha(v_n - v) \leq t, \forall n \geq n_0(\alpha, t) \rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} q_\alpha(v_n - v) \leq t, \forall t > 0 \rightarrow \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} q_\alpha(v_n - v) = 0$. Therefore, (v_n) is \check{L} -converges to v with respect to Q .

Proposition 4.7: Let $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ be a FRNS satisfying (RN₆) and (x_n) be a sequence in V , then (x_n) is a \check{L} -Cauchy sequence in $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ if and only if (v_n) is a \check{L} -Cauchy sequence in (V, Q) .

Proof:

Suppose that (x_n) be a \check{L} -Cauchy sequence in $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$, then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{N}_f(v_n - v_{n+s}) = 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty, s > 0$ and $\forall t > 0 \leftrightarrow \forall 0 \leq \alpha < 1 \exists n_0(\alpha, t) > 0$ with $\tilde{N}_f(v_n - v_{n+s}) < \alpha \forall n \geq n_0(\alpha, t), \forall s > 0 \leftrightarrow q_\alpha |v_{n+s} - v_n| = 0 \forall s > 0 \leftrightarrow (v_n)$ is a \check{L} -Cauchy sequence in (V, Q) .

Proposition 4.8: If $(V, \tilde{N}_f, \Delta_c)$ be a FRNS satisfying an \check{L} -complete property then (V, Q) is a \check{L} -complete GSQNF.

Proof: The evidence is clear.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an investigation was conducted between real normed space and fuzzy real normed space (FRNS). After presenting the notion of the family of star sublinear functional and through pioneering analysis of their reciprocal interactions, we've been able to advance both disciplines and increase their attractiveness. Additionally, the concept of generating space of quasinorm and quasi-norm family (GSQNF) has been presented, and with the formation of the theory of decomposition theorem for an FRN (\tilde{N}_f) into a family of quasinorm. Several findings regarding fuzzy functional analysis can be easily deduced from the corresponding formulations in functional analysis.

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